

“My book is different from the traditional reading experience. I didn’t want it to be the sort of book that symbolises knowledge and configures readers as receivers of knowledge.”

According to Reynolds, *Prismatic Jane Eyre: Close-Reading a World Novel Across Languages* was never going to be an ordinary book. Just as *Jane Eyre* is not just an English book – it has been translated into many different languages, with each translation creating shifts in interpretation, understanding, language, voice and style. There are now many *Janes*, says Reynolds, who led the *Prismatic Jane Eyre* research project, which culminated in an open access volume.

Reynolds collaborated with many academics from around the world and he wanted the book to reflect the international input and the nature of the work – that literature is not restricted to one language, one interpretation or one voice.

He said: “Reviewing all this work by translators and publishers in different locations is creative work. It’s collaborative and creative, remaking and discovering new significances in new locations.”

Being open access and born digital, there was much more flexibility over the book’s form, language and content. The different authors had more freedom to write in their own voice and style, and the text includes digital interactive maps and verbal animations.

Reynolds says this approach helps break down disciplinary and traditional academic silos, leading to greater creative expression.

Matthew Reynolds,
Professor of English
and Comparative
Criticism at Oxford
University

Reynolds thinks
publishing open access
benefits research

It enables authors to
explore the potential
of digital

It breaks down
barriers, encouraging
interdisciplinary
working

New ways of
publishing encourage
innovation and new
research outputs

It encourages
diversity of thinking